

ROOSTING HABITS AND BEHAVIOR OF NORTHERN LONG-EARED BATS ON NANTUCKET

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ABSTRACT

The federally threatened northern long-eared bat (*Myotis septentrionalis*) appears to be persisting on Nantucket and in other coastal areas, despite dramatic population declines across the inland Northeast, associated with the spread of White Nose Syndrome. We expanded on mist-netting, radio-tracking, and acoustic survey efforts from 2016 to better characterize northern long-eared bat behavior and habitat use on the island. We also partnered with graduate students from UNH and UAlbany to collect swab and tissue samples for WNS and genetic testing. We captured a total of 36 bats, all northern long-eareds, and tagged 13 individuals. In July, we tracked 6 bats to a total of 9 roosts located within 3 km of their capture location. Bats were found roosting in mature pitch pine trees and snags, as well as under shingles or trim boards on houses sided with cedar shingles. Mist-netting led to the capture of both lactating female bats and healthy juveniles; emergence counts revealed maternity colonies of at least 7-18 individuals. In October, we tracked 3 bats to a total of 6 roosts, which were used for multiple nights in succession. One bat roosted in a pitch pine, but the other locations were structural roosts on houses and barns, and in one case, in a crawl space.

BACKGROUND

The northern long-eared bat (*Myotis septentrionalis*) is a small, insectivorous, forest-dwelling bat of the family Vespertilionidae (MA NHESP 2012). Historically common, this species has seen population declines of 90-99% in the northeastern United States due to the spread of White Nose Syndrome (WNS) (Turner et al. 2011). WNS is a fungal disease caused by *Pseudogymnoascus destructans* (*P.d.*), which grows over the bodies of infected bats during hibernation, leading to frequent arousal, loss of water and fat reserves, and eventual death (Turner et al. 2011). The northern long-eared bat is now endangered in Massachusetts (MA NHESP 2017), and is listed as threatened under the federal Endangered Species Act (USFWS 2013).

Before the outbreak of WNS, northern long-eared bats were common on Cape Cod and Martha's Vineyard (Buresch 1999, Army National Guard 2000). Recent studies have suggested that despite declines elsewhere, the species is persisting in coastal Massachusetts and on Long Island (Curry 2016, Johnson et al. 2016, Hoff et al. 2016). On Martha's Vineyard, researchers documented lactating females maintaining maternity colonies of up to 15 individuals, and captured volant juvenile bats (Johnson et al. 2016). There are no pre-WNS studies of bats on Nantucket, but an NBI-sponsored acoustic inventory of bats in 2015 documented the presence of *Myotis* species at multiple sites on the eastern part of Nantucket, with probable northern long-eared bat calls at Norwood Farm, Squam Farm, and Stump Pond (Dowling 2016). In 2016, with NBI funding, I worked with the Nantucket Conservation Foundation to conduct an exploratory mist-netting and radio-tracking study. We captured nine northern long-eared bats in the summer, including both healthy lactating females and volant juveniles of both sexes. In October, we captured an adult male northern long-eared bat, which we tracked to a hibernation site it shared with at least four other individuals.

Given their decline at inland sites, it is important to conserve northern long-eared bats in places like Nantucket where they appear to be persisting. In this study, we expanded on prior work to further characterize habitat use by northern long-eared bats on the island. Northern long-eared bats are traditionally thought of as "deep forest" bats, which roost in trees and prefer large tracts of mature forest. On Nantucket, however, we have recorded acoustic activity in a variety of settings, including open scrub oak habitat, and found bats using roosts in human structures. Our goal with this research was to help inform any management efforts that may be necessary to help the species continue to thrive on the island. In addition, we partnered with Samantha Hoff, of University of New York – Albany and Meghan Stark to collect and analyze tissue and swab samples from captured bats for genetic and WNS testing. The results of these analyses may help elucidate why northern long-eared bats are persisting on Nantucket.

METHODS

Bat Capture and Radio-transmitter Attachment

We captured bats using single and triple-high set-ups of 4-6 m mist nets strung across woods roads and paths, during trapping sessions in July, August, and October of 2017. We trapped from near sunset until 4-5 hours post-sunset, depending on trapping success and weather conditions. All bats were handled in accordance with American Society of Mammalogists standards (Sikes & Gannon 2011). Bats were identified to species, aged, sexed, weighed, and measured along the forearm. From most northern long-eared bats, we obtained a wing-punch biopsy for genetic testing, and in the fall, we swabbed the bat's forearm and muzzle to obtain a sample to test for *P.d.* For a subset of captured adult northern long-eared bats, we also shaved between the scapulae, and attached a 0.3 g VHF radio-tag (Advanced Telemetry Systems, Asanti, MN) using animal ID tag cement (Nasco) or eyelash adhesive. To ensure bat safety, no transmitter constituted greater than 5% of bat body weight (Aldridge & Brigham 1988). All gear was treated in accordance with the USFWS National White-Nose Syndrome Decontamination Protocol (2016).

We manually tracked bats to roost sites daily, and recorded roost locations and characteristics. Where possible, emergence counts were conducted from approximately ½ hour before sunset to ½ hour after sunset to estimate colony size. Under circumstances where emergence counts were not possible, we commonly checked for a radio signal post-sunset to determine if the tagged bat had emerged.

We conducted passive acoustic surveys at 5 sites on Nantucket and 2 sites on Tuckernuck, for periods of 4-337 nights, depending on the site. We used an ANABAT II or SM4BatFS acoustic detector to record calls, and processed data through KaleidoscopePro, an auto-classification program that identifies recorded bat calls to species.

RESULTS

Bat Capture and Morphometrics

We mist-netted for bats for a total of 10 nights in 2017. In July, we trapped for two nights at the Ram Pasture property where we had successfully captured northern long-eared bats in 2016; we also trapped for one night each at Head of the Plains and Lost Farm. In August, Nantucket Conservation Foundation staff trapped for two nights at Ram Pasture, and one night at a private residence on Burnt Swamp Lane. In October, we trapped for two nights at Ram Pasture and one night at Lost Farm, and also hand-captured several bats at roosts.

We captured a total of 36 bats in 2017, which were all northern long-eared bats. Forearm length among captured bats varied from 33.3- 37.6 mm; weight varied from 5.25-9.4 g. Excluding one cold night (8°C at start) when we caught no bats, we captured an average of 2.0 bats per hour, or 3.8 bats per night, using either 2 single-high nets, or 2 single-high and 1 triple-high net. At Ram Pasture, where we recorded particularly high acoustic activity, we caught an average of 3.0 bats per hour, or 4.6 bats per night.

In July, we caught a total of 8 adult females, 2 juvenile males, and 5 juvenile females. No juveniles were captured in our first night of mist-netting (18 July), but on subsequent nights we captured volant juveniles trapping ~ 1 km away (21 July) and at the same site (22 July), suggesting we may have been trapping at the initiation of the volancy period, when juveniles are just beginning to venture out to forage. Adult females captured in July tended to weigh more than juvenile males and females (Table 1), and all were lactating. In August, we captured 6 adult females, 1 adult male, 2 juvenile males, and 1 juvenile female. In October, we captured 3 adult females and 6 adult males in mist-nets. We also hand-captured 2 adult male bats - one in the crawl space on Millbrook Road we identified as a hibernaculum in 2016, the other under a pool umbrella in the Deer Run neighborhood. At this late point in the season, it was difficult to distinguish adults from juveniles, and some bats identified as adults may have been young-of-the-year. Bats captured in October weighed more on average than bats captured during the summer months (Table 1).

Of the 11 bats sampled for WNS in the fall on Nantucket, one tested positive for low levels of *P.d.* (Samantha Hoff, personal communication), although it appeared healthy at the time of capture. Genetic testing will ultimately help determine if bats on the island are genetically isolated from mainland populations.

Bat Radio-tagging, Roost Tracking, and Emergence Counts

We radio-tagged and tracked 8 bats in July and 5 bats in October (Table 2).

In July, we tracked 6 bats to a total of 9 roosts. Poor tag retention resulted in short tracking periods – one bat was not re-located, one bat dropped its tag on the night of capture, and the remaining 6 bats were tracked to 1- 2 roosts each, over tracking periods of less than 3 days. We observed roosting habits similar to those seen in our small exploratory tracking study in 2016. We tracked bats to both house and tree roosts, although individual bats were only found in either house or tree roosts. All tree roosts were in pitch pines (*Pinus rigida*), in mature trees with DBH of 29.8-41.2 cm, which were currently or previously dominant or emergent trees in the canopy. Several roost trees were dead and had broken tops, so tree height at time of bat use varied from 6-12 m. Most trees had obvious potential roost sites, such as broken limbs or trunks which might allow entrance into a tree cavity, or loose bark on dead trees. Bats were typically observed emerging from roosts located high in roost trees, but at one tree we observed bats roosting under loose bark on a dead pitch pine only 1.5 m above ground level. We identified two house roosts in the Deer Run neighborhood where we had found individual bats roosting in the summer and fall of 2016. We also found one bat roosting in a house to the north of the Deer Run neighborhood, 2.7 km from its capture site at Ram Pasture. All three house roosts were in buildings with cedar shingle siding, in neighborhoods set within stands of pitch pine. The first roost locations identified for each bat were 179-2734 m from their capture location; distances between consecutive roosts was only 60-91 m (Table 2).

Of the 4 bats tracked for multiple days in July, only one appeared to return to the same roost for a second night. This bat was roosting in a house in a gated yard, and so the initial roost location

was approximate - the bat could also have switched roosts, albeit within a small area on the gated property.

The highest emergence count was for F023, which shared its first roost tree with at least 17 other bats. We performed a second night of emergence counts, observing both the original roost and new roost tree used by this bat. The second night also yielded a total of 18 bats, split evenly between the two trees, which may represent the full size of this maternity colony. Two other tagged bats were observed emerging with 6 and 7 other bats respectively in July.

In October, one bat was not re-located and one bat dropped its tag on the night of capture, but the remaining three bats showed better tag retention than in the summer months. Because bats did not always emerge on cold nights, it could be difficult to distinguish a dropped tag from a torpid bat, but these three bats retained tags for at least 6-16 days. Each bat was tracked to two roosts, which were used for multiple nights. F123 was tracked to two house roosts in the Deer Run neighborhood. M183 was tracked to two house roosts by the southeast corner of Hummock Pond. F103 was tracked to a barn roost west of Lost Farm and to a tree roost in the Lost Farm forest. The first roosts identified for tagged bats were 1483-2332 m from their capture locations; bats subsequently moved 74-772 m between roosts (Table 2).

The sole fall tree roost was in a live pitch pine, which had similar characteristics to the summer roost sites. The tree was a mature, canopy-level tree, with a DBH of 35.5 cm and height of 10.5 m. A potential roost was evident in a broken branch that was still attached to the tree. Three of the roosts in human structures were in houses with cedar shingles, one was in a barn/workshop with plain wood vertical siding, and one was in a house with brown painted clapboards. Most structural roosts appeared to be under shingles or trim boards, but the second roost used by M183 was at or below ground level, and appeared to be in the northeast corner of a crawl space. We initially suspected this might be a hibernation site, but the bat left the crawl space and disappeared before we gained permission from the landowner to access the space. Four additional northern long-eared bat roosts were identified in the fall – one under a trim board at the house next door to F103's barn roost, one at the Millbrook Road crawl space, and two under poolside umbrellas in the Deer Run neighborhood. The structure roosts in the Deer Run

neighborhood were set amidst stands of pitch pines in areas with significant tree cover, as were the roosts used by F103 and the two bats in the neighboring house. However, M183 roosted in an open area composed of a mix of sandplain grassland, coastal shrubland and coastal pond shore vegetation communities. There were some low-growing Japanese pine, but little to no canopy cover.

It appeared some bats were roosting singly in the fall, but we observed F103 emerging from her barn roost with one other bat, and two bats were roosting under the trim board at the neighboring house. Of the three bats tagged in the fall, F103 was the only bat to return to her first roost site after moving to the second. She subsequently returned to the second roost, before disappearing.

Acoustics

Northern long-eared bats were identified as present ($p < 0.05$) at four of five sites sampled on Nantucket (Table 3). They were not identified at the UMass Field Station during 5 nights of sampling, although little brown bats (*Myotis lucifugus*) were identified. The calls of species within the *Myotis* genus can be difficult to distinguish, and it is possible calls auto-classified as little brown bats at this site were actually made by northern long-eared bats. No northern long-eared bat calls were identified on Tuckernuck, but at one site, little brown bats were identified as present on 2 of 5 nights sampled.

Nantucket Conservation Foundation staff worked with Samantha Hoff to conduct extensive short-term monitoring across a sampling grid laid over much of the island. Samantha will be constructing a presence-absence model, based on manual vetting of calls identified as northern long-eared bats by auto-classification software.

DISCUSSION

Nantucket continues to support reproducing colonies of northern long-eared bats, with both lactating females and juveniles of healthy weight captured in our July mist-netting. We counted at least 11 individuals in a maternity colony in 2016; this year, we counted at least 18 bats

sharing a maternity roost. There is much on-going discussion in the bat research community regarding the reason for the persistence of northern long-eared bats in coastal areas – particularly on Nantucket and Long Island, but also to a lesser degree on Martha’s Vineyard and at other locations in coastal Massachusetts (Curry 2016, Johnson et al. 2016, Hoff et al. 2016). One explanation for their continued survival could be isolation from inland bat populations and inland hibernation sites infected with WNS. Based on our observations from last year, and entry by Danielle O’Dell into the Millbrook Road hibernaculum in February 2017, we know some bats are hibernating locally on the island and could be isolated from WNS, but given the presence of a WNS-positive bat in our sampling this year, it is clear that not all are. The relative isolation of offshore islands may merely have delayed the spread of WNS, which could ultimately spread throughout Nantucket and lead to a population collapse. Capture rates on Martha’s Vineyard have decreased significantly from pre-WNS levels (Baldwin et al. 2017); a WNS-positive bat was active on Martha’s Vineyard in February 2017 during a warm spell, and subsequently died (Luanne Johnson, personal communication).

On the other hand, research on Long Island suggests bats there show exposure to the disease, but continue to persist in significant numbers (Carl Herzog, personal communication). It is possible that genotypic or behavioral differences are shielding coastal bat populations from the worst ravages of WNS. There is some speculation, for example, that persistence of these bats in coastal areas could be driven by behavioral differences associated with the moderate marine climate. Northern long-eared bats living on Long Island, NY hibernate for almost a month less than their upstate, inland counterparts (Carl Herzog, personal communication). If bats are able to shorten the hibernation period, and actively forage during warm periods throughout the winter in marine climates, it is possible additional fuel and water resources accumulated during these times could allow them to survive WNS infection. Deployment of acoustic detectors during the winter months at potential foraging sites would be a useful method to assess the possibility of bat foraging bouts in winter, as would winter insect trapping. Our data from winter 2016 showed a significant decrease in total bat calls and number of nights with activity as the temperature dropped in October and November, but we still picked up occasional *Myotis* spp. calls well into December.

Our tracking results expanded the number of roosts identified compared to the previous year, but provided a similar overall picture to that suggested by our limited data from 2016. Northern long-eared bats on Nantucket appear to form maternity colonies of comparable size, and switch summer roosts with similar frequency, to members of the species studied elsewhere (Silvis et al. 2016). We found bats using both human structures and trees. Tree roosts were found at a variety of heights and aspects, over a range of understory and midstory plants, and under a range of canopy cover, but were found solely in mature live and dead pitch pines. Identified roosts in human structures were primarily associated with cedar shingles, although not exclusively. Northern long-eared bats are known to be opportunistic in selecting tree roosts, and will roost in a variety of tree species (Silvis et al. 2016). Observed roost site choices may represent a sampling of the available roost habitat, rather than a preference for a particular tree species or structural siding type. Island-wide, there are almost 3,000 acres of pine-dominated woodland (including black pine), compared to less than 300 acres of mixed deciduous forest (The Nature Conservancy 1998); nearly 99% of houses on Nantucket have at least partial cedar shingle siding (John Hedden, personal communication).

Most structure roosts identified were in areas with a high percentage of tree cover, but one bat used house roosts in open scrubland habitat on the southeast side of Hummock Pond. Northern long-eared bats typically avoid open habitat (Owen et al. 2003, 2004; Patriquin and Barclay 2003; Henderson and Broders 2008), so it was unexpected to find one roosting in an area with so little tree cover. Future research could utilize acoustic surveys to consider bat use of open habitats on the island. Our tracking data suggest that bats do cross relative large expanses of open country – two of the 13 bats tracked in this study traversed at least 0.6 km of open habitat between a pitch pine stand at Head of the Plains, and the larger pitch pine forest around Ram Pasture.

In keeping with our pilot study results from 2016, movements between capture sites and roost sites were longer than typically recorded elsewhere (Silvis et al. 2016, Baldwin et al. 2017), which could suggest a relative paucity of either foraging or roosting habitat, requiring longer-distance movements. We observed short distance movements between consecutive roosts during the summer months, as has been commonly observed elsewhere. We have limited data, but it

appeared bats could be moving somewhat longer distances in the fall, although still under 1 km. If further research supports a difference in roosting habitat range between the summer and fall, it could suggest bats must move further because there are fewer roosts that meet microclimate conditions necessary during cooler weather. Alternatively, fall bats may be less tied to small roosting ranges than lactating females, which in July are maintaining maternity colonies and moving pups or care-taking newly volant young.

Unfortunately, we were not able to identify hibernation sites this year. The two bats which disappeared from roosts in late October may have traveled off-island; alternatively, they may have moved to other on-island sites which were far enough from their last known location to render subsequent detection unlikely or where the radio signal was muffled. We know very little about the timing of northern long-eared bat departure from summer territories to fall swarming and hibernation sites. Congeneric little brown bats leave summer maternity roosts and begin swarming at hibernacula between July and October (Cope 1976, Schowalter 1980, Kunz et al. 1998, Townsend et al. 2008, Burns et al. 2014), and two little brown bats tagged on Martha's Vineyard in 2016 left the island between late August and early September (Dowling et al. 2017). Based on this evidence, we might expect bats roosting on Nantucket in late October and November to be hibernating locally. Tree cavities may provide habitat to hibernating *Myotis* bats in moderate marine-influenced climates (Burles et al. 2014). In North Carolina, one northern long-eared bat was recorded switching among tree roosts in late December, when temperatures were below 0°C (Gary Jordan, personal observation). Structure roosts in heated buildings could also be providing hibernation habitat, as we discovered in 2016. However, in Nebraska, northern long-eared bats were detected making migratory movements of up to 41 km to a cave hibernation site as late as November, following multi-day periods in which they roosted in trees and did not emerge (White et al. 2017). Is it therefore impossible to conclude whether the ultimate hibernation destination of bats tracked into early November was on Nantucket or off-island.

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TABLES AND FIGURES

	Forearm length (mm)	Weight (g)
adult female	36.1 ± 1.0	7.3 ± 0.6 summer 8.1 ± 0.3 fall
adult male	35.5 ± 0.8	6.0 summer 8.5 ± 0.6 fall
juvenile female	35.3 ± 1.0	6.3 ± 0.3 summer
juvenile male	35.6 ± 1.8	6.0 ± 0.5 summer

Table 1 Forearm length (mm) and weight (g) for northern long-eared bats captured on Nantucket in summer and fall 2017 (mean ± SD).

Bat ID	Capture date	Capture location	Days tracked	# of roosts identified	Maximum emergence count	Distance from capture site to first re-location (m)	Distance between roosts (m)
F083	7/18/2017	Ram Pasture	0+	0	-	-	-
F023	7/18/2017	Ram Pasture	2	2	18	266	87
F003	7/18/2017	Ram Pasture	0	0	-	-	-
F043	7/20/2017	Head of the Plains	1+	1	8	961	-
F084	7/21/2017	Lost Farm	1+	1	0	179	-
F024	7/22/2017	Ram Pasture	2	1	-	2734	-
F044	7/22/2017	Ram Pasture	2+	2	7	1531	91
F063	7/22/2017	Ram Pasture	2+	2	0	2304	60
M163	10/18/2017	Ram Pasture	0	0	-	-	-
M143	10/18/2017	Ram Pasture	0+	0	-	953	-
M183	10/18/2017	Ram Pasture	16	2	0	1483	74
F103	10/18/2017	Ram Pasture	12	2	2	2332	772
F123	10/18/2017	Ram Pasture	6+	2	-	2021	228

Table 2 Tracking data for northern long-eared bats captured on Nantucket in summer and fall 2017. (+) indicates tagged bat left roost or capture site, but dropped tag before roosting.

Site		EPFU	LABO	LACI	LANO	MYLE	MYLU	MYSE	MYSO	PESU
RAM PASTURE										
1/3/2017-9/12/2017 (ANABAT)	# of nights detected	122	132	67	28	50	155	152	63	44
10/12/2017-12/5/2017 (SM4BatFS)	# of calls	842	795	989	41	73	11636	2770	103	93
n=240	# of nights "present"	88	39	51	3	904	146	120	0	5
SQUAM FARM										
5/30/17-6/13/2017 (ANABAT)	# of nights detected	1	5	1	1	0	1	6	1	1
n=10	# of calls	1	6	125	29	0	1	9	1	1
	# of nights "present"	0	5	1	0	0	0	6	0	1
LOST FARM										
6/9/2017-12/9/2017 (SM4BatFS)	# of nights detected	13	29	13	13	2	25	34	10	7
n=53	# of calls	19	76	285	14	2	96	3943	11	21
	# of nights "present"	2	22	10	0	2	11	34	0	4
HEAD OF THE PLAINS										
7/14/2017-7/17/2017 (ANABAT)	# of nights detected	2	0	1	0	0	2	4	2	0
n=4	# of calls	2	0	1	0	0	2	195	4	0
	# of nights "present"	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0
TUCKERNUCK (1)										
8/1/2017-8/5/2017 (SM4BatFS)	# of nights detected	0	5	0	4	0	5	0	1	4
n=5	# of calls	0	447	0	6	0	135	0	1	22
	# of nights "present"	0	5	0	1	0	2	0	0	0
TUCKERNUCK (2)										
8/6/2017-8/13/2017 (SM4BatFS)	# of nights detected	2	2	2	2	0	2	0	0	2
n=7	# of calls	12	41	56	6	0	8	0	0	3
	# of nights "present"	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	1
UMASS FIELD STATION										
10/5/2017-10/9/2017 (SM4BatFS)	# of nights detected	0	3	0	1	0	3	0	0	0
n=5	# of calls	0	5	0	1	0	64	0	0	0
	# of nights "present"	0	2	0	0	0	3	0	0	0

Table 3 Species identification of acoustic recordings based on auto-classification by KaleidoscopePro. EPFU = *Eptesicus fuscus*, LABO=*Lasiurus borealis*, LACI=*L. cinereus*, LANO=*Lasionycteris noctivagans*, MYLE=*Myotis leibii*, MYLU=*M. lucifugus*, MYSE=*M. septentrionalis*, MYSO=*M. sodalis*, PESU=*Perimyotis subflavus*. # of nights "present" indicates number of nights auto-classification software identified bat as present with probability of error $p < 0.05$. The acoustic detector type used is listed in parentheses after dates of sampling.

a)

b)

Figure 1 a) summer and b) fall trapping and tracking locations, where \square = mist-netting site, Δ = roost site, X = dropped tag. Locations for individual bats are differentiated by color. In a) summer, all shades of blue represent bats trapped at the blue mist-net location. In b) fall, all colored roost and dropped tag locations represent bats trapped at red mist-net location. White roost sites were identified in visual surveys.

APPENDIX I: Summaries of Locations for Individual Tagged Bats

F083 was tagged at Ram Pasture (41.26977, -70.15544) on 18 July 2017. The bat dropped its tag on the night of capture, which was found on 19 July in dense scrub 0.58 km from the capture site at (41.26663, -70.14983).

F023 was tagged at Ram Pasture (41.26977, -70.15544) on 18 July 2017. This bat was tracked to a tree roost in Ram Pasture on 19 July (41.26745, -70.15622). Based on an emergence count that night, the bat appeared to be using a hole in the broken top on the east side of the tree to access a roost in the trunk. At least 18 bats emerged from the roost between 20:29 and 20:47. The bat was tracked to a second tree roost in Ram Pasture on 20 July (41.268235, -70.156214). The roost tree had a broken top and ~50% bark remaining. Bats were visible under flaking bark at about 1.5 m above ground level, where the radio signal was also strongest. That night, 9 bats were observed emerging from this roost between 20:24-20:46. Meanwhile, 9 bats were observed emerging from the first roost tree for this bat between 20:23-20:41. On 21 July, the bat had dropped its tag at the second roost. That night, one bat was observed visiting the first roost tree at 20:28, and two bats were observed in the vicinity of the second roost tree, but it was not clear that multiple bats emerged from either tree. On 22 July, again one bat appeared to emerge from the first roost tree, and none from the second tree. Multiple bats were observed in the vicinity of both trees, including 2-3 bats circling the first roost tree from 20:26-20:42.

F003 was tagged at Ram Pasture (41.26977, -70.15544) on 18 July 2017. The bat was not re-located after release.

F043 was tagged at Head of the Plains (41.26794, -70.16695) on 20 July. This bat was tracked to a tree roost in Ram Pasture on 21 July (41.26733, -70.15548). That night, 8 bats were observed emerging from between two large dead branches on the east side of the tree between 20:28-20:36. The bat dropped its tag in Ram Pasture that night, and the tag was found on 22 July (41.26955, -70.15571). That night, 6 bats were observed emerging from the roost tree between 20:27-20:48, with an additional 3 bats observed in the vicinity.

F084 was tagged at Lost Farm (41.26886, -70.13773) on 21 July. This bat was tracked to a tree roost at Lost Farm on 22 July (41.26863, -70.13561). On 23 July, the dropped tag was found nearby, at (41.26943, -70.13596).

F024 was tagged at Ram Pasture (41.26977, -70.15544) on 22 July 2017. This bat was tracked to a presumed structure roost on 23 July (41.282504, -70.127449). We could not access the property to locate the exact roost location, but based on the radio signal, the bat emerged that night at ~20:29, and was tracked to the roost the following day. The bat dropped its tag in the roost on 24 July. The transmitter was localized to the west side of the house on 1 August, and appeared to be stuck under a cedar shingle.

F044 was tagged at Ram Pasture (41.26977, -70.15544) on 22 July 2017. On 23 July, the bat was tracked to a tree roost on the Lost Farm property, 1.5 km from the capture location (41.26763, -70.13735). No bats were observed emerging from the roost that night, but on 24 July the bat was tracked to a second tree roost in the same forest stand (41.26842, -70.13708).

The second tree was immediately adjacent to the Lost Farm driveway. Seven bats were observed emerging from and circling this tree and adjacent trees between 20:34-20:46 that night. The bat dropped its tag at the roost on 24 July.

F063 was tagged at Ram Pasture (41.26977, -70.15544) on 22 July 2017. F063 was tracked to a house roost in the Deer Run neighborhood on the day following capture (41.27019, -70.12788). The bat appeared to be roosting on the west side of the house under a shingle or rakeboard. The bat was not observed emerging that night, but based on the radio signal, exited shortly after dusk. On 24 July, the bat was tracked to a nearby house, where the bat appeared to be roosting on the east side of the house under a shingle, or in the attic vent or chimney (41.26966, -70.12778). The bat emerged and dropped its tag that night near the first roost, where it was found on 25 July (41.269969, -70.127948).

M163 was tagged at Ram Pasture (41.26977, -70.15544) on 18 October 2017. This bat was not re-located after release.

M143 was tagged at Ram Pasture (41.26977, -70.15544) on 18 October 2017. This bat dropped its tag the night of capture, which was found beneath a tree in a pitch pine stand at Head of the Plains on 19 October (41.26723, -70.166332).

F123 was tagged at Ram Pasture (41.26977, -70.15544) on 18 October 2017. This bat was tracked to a house roost in the Deer Run neighborhood on 19 October (41.26984, -70.13125). The bat returned to this roost, or failed to emerge, through 23 October, although the transmitter signal was poor and difficult to localize. It was tracked to a second house roost in the same neighborhood on 24 October (41.27047, -70.128651). It appeared to have dropped its tag at the roost.

F103 was tagged at Ram Pasture (41.26977, -70.15544) on 18 October 2017. This bat was tracked to barn/workshop (41.26736, -70.12772) located 2.3 km from the capture location on 19 October. The barn was covered in vertical siding composed of weathered wood, and the bat appeared to be roosting under a piece of loose siding at about 2 m above ground level on the southwest side of the structure. The bat was observed emerging at 18:15 that night with one other bat. The following night the bat was tracked to the same roost site, and emerged ~18:30. The bat had returned to the roost on 21 October, and continued to use the roost through 24 October. It was lost for several days, but ultimately tracked to a second roost in a tree in the Lost Farm pitch pine forest on 27 October (41.2688668, -70.1367325). This bat failed to emerge on 27 October, but during warmer conditions, emerged on 28 October and returned to the barn roost. The bat remained at the barn roost through the evening of 2 November. The bat was located at the tree roost at Lost Farm on 3 November, and had disappeared on 5 November.

M183 was tagged at Ram Pasture (41.26977, -70.15544) on 18 October 2017. M183 was tracked to a small cottage beside Hummock Pond (41.25682, -70.15122), 1.5 km from the capture location, on 19 October. The bat appeared to be roosting under the trim board or shingle on the south side of the house. We did not directly observe the bat emerge, but based on the radio signal, the bat emerged at 18:30 on 19 October, returned to the roost the following day, and

emerged that night at 18:35. The bat continued to use the roost through 24 October. The bat was lost for several days, but then tracked to a second roost in a nearby crawl space on 28 October (41.256888, -70.150342). The bat continued to use that roost through 1 November, when the landowners returned to the property. On 3 November, the bat had disappeared.